

1D RELATIVISTIC CONFINED COULOMB PROBLEM FOR DIRAC EQUATION ($Z < 137$)

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Consider first the case of quantum particle confined in a impenetrable relativistic box of size L . Such system can be described by stationary one dimensional Dirac equation which is given by (natural units, $\hbar = m = c = 1$)

$$H_0\psi = (-i\alpha\nabla + \beta)\psi = \varepsilon\psi \quad (1)$$

where α, β are the well known Dirac matrices.

In the Dirac representation, the four-component Dirac spinor ψ , can be expressed in terms of the large and small two-component semi-spinors, $\phi = \begin{pmatrix} \phi_1 \\ \phi_2 \end{pmatrix}$ and $\chi = \begin{pmatrix} \chi_1 \\ \chi_2 \end{pmatrix}$ respectively.

That is,

$$\psi = \begin{pmatrix} \phi \\ \chi \end{pmatrix}$$

Equation (1) is equivalent to the following coupled equations:

$$-i\sigma \cdot \nabla\chi + \phi = \varepsilon\phi \quad -i\sigma \cdot \nabla\phi - \chi = \varepsilon\chi$$

where, σ - Pauli matrices.

Using one can find energy levels with $k = \sqrt{\varepsilon^2 - 1}$

Solution of Eq.(1) for the boundary condition, $\phi_1(0) = \phi_1(L) = 0$ can be written as following

$$\psi(x) = A \begin{pmatrix} i\sin(kx) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{k}{\varepsilon + 1} \cos(kx) \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow$$

$$\Rightarrow \phi_n(x) = A_n \begin{pmatrix} i\sin(k_n x) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{k_n}{\varepsilon_n + 1} \cos(k_n x) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where,

$$k_n = n\pi/L, n = 1, 2, \dots \quad \varepsilon_n = \sqrt{k_n^2 + 1}.$$

In Eq.(2), we determine the coefficient A_n by introducing the notation

$$B_n = \frac{k_n}{\varepsilon_n + 1}$$

Based on the normalization condition,

$$\int_0^L |\phi_n(x)|^2 dx = 1 \Rightarrow$$

$$\Rightarrow A_n = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L(B_n^2 - 1)}} \quad (3)$$

Substituting Eq.(3) into Eq.(2), we get the following

$$\phi_n(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L(B_n^2 - 1)}} \begin{pmatrix} \text{isin}(k_n x) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ B_n \cos(k_n x) \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$H\psi = E\psi \quad (5)$$

Given that,

$$H = H_0 + V(x), H_0\phi_n = \varepsilon_n\phi_n, \psi = \sum C_n\phi_n, \delta_{mn} = \int \phi_m^*\phi_n dx$$

the following can be obtained from Eq.(5).

$$\begin{aligned} [H_0 + V(x)]\psi &= E\psi \Rightarrow \\ \Rightarrow \sum C_n H_0\phi_n + \sum C_n V\phi_n &= E \sum C_n\phi_n \Rightarrow \\ \Rightarrow \sum C_n \varepsilon_n\phi_n + \sum C_n V\phi_n &= E \sum C_n\phi_n \end{aligned}$$

We multiply both sides of the above equation by ϕ_m^* and integrate. After that, we have the following equation.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum C_n \varepsilon_n \delta_{mn} + \sum C_n \int \phi_m^* V\phi_n dx &= E \sum C_n \delta_{mn} \Rightarrow \\ \Rightarrow C_n \varepsilon_n + \sum C_n V_{mn} &= C_n E \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\varepsilon_n C_n + \sum V_{mn} C_n = E C_n \quad (6)$$

In the Eq.(6),

$$V_{mn} = \int \phi_m^* V\phi_n dx$$

The Coulomb potential was generally expressed as follows

$$V(x) = -\frac{Z}{a + |x|}$$

We assume that the particle moves along the x axis in a bounded interval.

That is,

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq x \leq L \Rightarrow x > 0 \Rightarrow \\ \Rightarrow V(x) &= -\frac{Z}{x + a} \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we can find energy levels of relativistic 1D hydrogen atom in box with the help of determining eigenvalues, i.e. diagonalizing of following matrix.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_1 - V_{11} & -V_{12} & \cdots & -V_{1N} \\ -V_{21} & \varepsilon_2 - V_{22} & \cdots & -V_{2N} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -V_{N1} & -V_{N2} & \cdots & \varepsilon_N - V_{NN} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Table. The energy spectra of a 1D relativistic hydrogen-like atom in box with the nuclear charge $\alpha = 300/137$ and box's size $L(m = 1, a = 1)$.

n	$L = 100$
1	0.931151040261464
2	0.932042822356621

3	0.932523381516482
4	0.934690887592249
5	0.937281069840522
6	0.938817990577198
7	0.944252087567858
8	0.948881003915669
9	0.950875387242086
10	0.958600554037474

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